

ADAPTIVE COMPOSITE PANEL WITH EMBEDDED SMA ACTUATORS: DESIGN, MANUFACTURING, TESTING

P. Terriault*, S. Lacasse, C. Simoneau, V. Brailovski

Mechanical Engineering Department, Ecole de technologie superieure, Montreal, Canada

* Corresponding author (patrick.terriault@etsmtl.ca)

Keywords: Adaptive panel, Shape memory alloys, Actuator, Carbon fiber reinforced composite, Design diagram, Finite element analysis.

Abstract

Adaptive structures are designed to modify their shape in order to optimize their performances. In this work, in order to obtain an adaptive panel that is as compact as possible, shape memory alloy wire actuators are embedded in a composite laminate. When the actuators are heated, their contraction bends the laminate.

This work aims at developing models and manufacturing technology applicable to adaptive panels actuated by SMA elements embedded into a passive composite laminate host structure. It is shown that it is possible to model the entire adaptive panel with significantly less elements when shell, beam and link elements are used instead of 3D solid elements. Also, a prototype has been manufactured and tested and even if the measurement of the actuators' temperature remains problematic, it is shown that the finite element model is able to predict accurately the deformed shape of the adaptive panel.

Introduction

An adaptive panel is a structure that possesses the ability to modify its shape according to the surrounding conditions to which it is subjected. These structures can be used for various applications such as antennas [1], mirror shaping [2,3], building structures [4], but they are mainly used in aero or hydrodynamic applications to improve the global efficiency, including drag and weight reduction of aircraft wings [5-8], marine propellers [9], helicopter blades [10-11] and wind turbines [12].

In this paper, an adaptive panel has been developed to be as compact as possible. For example, the morphing wing designed in [5] is actuated by wires made of shape memory alloys (SMA) that are located inside an experimental wing. Unfortunately, the space inside a real wing usually contains structural members and fuel tanks. Therefore, it would become advantageous to insert the SMA

wires within the deformable panel similarly to the work of [13]. Unfortunately, numerical models being able to predict the behaviour of such adaptive panels are lacking.

Indeed, this work aims at developing numerical models and manufacturing technology applicable to an SMA-driven adaptive panel, which comprises a series of active SMA elements embedded into a passive composite laminate host structure (Fig. 1). A combined use of SMA actuators possessing extremely high work-generation potential [14] and laminated composites, demonstrating an excellent strength-to-weight ratio, should provide several benefits.

Fig. 1. Schematization of the adaptive panel.

Given that a composite laminate can be arranged in many different ways and that the aim of this paper is to present a design methodology, a particular layout is chosen. To facilitate the panel's bending during actuation, the host structure is assumed to be a composite laminate made of four uniaxial carbon fiber plies that are all oriented in the same direction, i.e. perpendicular to the SMA wire actuators. The actuators are positioned between the third and fourth ply so that when they are heated, they contract and create a bending moment in the host panel due to their out-of neutral plane location. Also, SMA actuators are inserted in polymer tubes called

“sheaths” so that they can freely slide inside the host structure. The SMA actuators are attached to the panel only at their extremities. The sheaths, embedded in the host structure during its manufacturing, provide two substantial benefits. First, the active elements can be easily removed, inspected and replaced. Second, the sheath electrically isolates the active element from the host structure, thus allowing more efficient Joule-heating of the actuator and protection from overheating of the surrounding laminate [15].

The first part of the paper presents a preliminary design diagram (PDD) that has been used to predict the deformation of the panel. This PDD studies only a small representative, symmetric and repetitive section of the panel. In the second part of the paper, the manufacturing technology of an adaptive panel and the experimental testing carried out to validate the PDD are discussed. Finally, the global finite element model (GFEM) is presented in the third section. This model is more versatile than the PDD since it can simulate the entire panel in which the actuators can be positioned arbitrarily without any constraint related to their repetitiveness or symmetries.

1 Preliminary design diagram (PDD)

The main idea behind the PDD is to model the host structure with structural 3D solid finite elements, and then to characterize experimentally the behaviour of the SMA actuators. Afterwards, both series of results are merged together to determine the possible equilibrium positions. Even if the GFEM (see section 3) is more versatile and economic in terms of calculation time than the PDD, the PDD is presented for two reasons: the GFEM was not yet developed at the beginning of the project and more importantly, the PDD represents a conceptual methodology based on static equilibrium that could be used in other works.

1.1 Finite element modeling of the host structure

A finite element model of the adaptive panel is built to link the panel's rigidity to its geometry for different axial strains generated by the contraction of the embedded active elements. The local thickening of the structure caused by the sheath, actuator and resin-rich zone in the vicinity of the active elements is taken into account (see Fig. 1). To reduce computing time, symmetry and repetition conditions are utilized: the width of the FEM is limited to a half-distance between two successive SMA wires

and its length is set to be as small as possible while showing a constant radius of curvature on at least 60% of its length. Therefore, only a small portion of the panel is studied as shown by the rectangular box pointed out by the white thick vertical arrow in Fig. 1.

The model, built in the ANSYS software environment, is divided into four parts: the composite laminate (upper and lower plies), the resin-rich zone, the sheath and the active element. The composite laminate is modeled by 20-node SOLID186 layered structural solid elements. These elements allow the user to specify the thickness, the orthotropic properties and the orientation of each ply which is meshed with one element in the Z (thickness) direction. The mesh size in the two other directions is fixed to be approximately equal to the ply thickness. The resin-rich zone, the sheath and the SMA element are meshed with 8-node SOLID186 homogeneous structural solid elements, given their isotropic mechanical properties. Even if only a small portion of the panel is modelled, the number of elements for the analysis is in the order of 300,000.

To simulate the SMA element's contraction during heating, a model of a conventional elastic material with a negative coefficient of thermal expansion is used as in [16]. The product of this negative coefficient with a temperature variation becomes the control parameter of the analysis that is called “induced axial strain”.

The results show a linear variation of the resulting actuator axial stress as a function of the resulting actuator axial strain (see Fig. 2). The solid lines represent the panel's stiffness for different distances between two successive SMA elements that vary between 20 and 100 mm. The markers on these lines correspond to different levels of induced axial strains (thin dashed lines) and radii of curvature (thick dashed curves). Note that a smaller radius of curvature represents a more pronounced bending of the panel.

It is important to emphasize the difference between the “induced axial strain” and the “resulting axial strain”. As defined previously, the induced strain corresponds to the product of the coefficient of thermal expansion with the temperature variation and it represents the maximum strain that can be reached by the SMA actuator upon heating, when no opposing force is applied. In reality, the actuator is embedded into the panel and therefore it is not free to contract. Consequently, the resulting strain of the

actuator embedded in the host structure will be smaller than the induced axial strain and the greater the panel stiffness, the greater will be this difference.

Fig. 2. Behaviour of the composite laminate.

From the results shown in Fig. 2, it is possible to determine the inter-actuator distance needed to obtain a prescribed radius of curvature for a given induced axial strain. It is then observed that if the inter-actuator distance decreases (i.e. more actuators in the panel), the actuators have to generate lower induced strains to reach the same radius of curvature. More details are available in [17].

1.2 SMA characterization

SMA actuators are $\varnothing 1\text{mm}$ wires made of a Ti-50.3at%Ni alloy supplied by SAES Getters. Given that the material is supplied in as-drawn condition (approximately 30% of cold work), post-deformation annealing needs to be performed to restore the alloy's shape memory properties. Each wire has been annealed during 1 hour at 550°C . Since the behavior of SMAs varies significantly during the first heating-cooling cycles, a 100-cycle stabilization routine was devised for this project. One stabilization cycle consisted of heating and cooling the specimen subjected to a given constant stress of 150 MPa. During the stabilisation routine, the wire was repeatedly heated by Joule effect from 25 to 150°C with subsequent free-convection cooling.

With the annealed and stabilized wires, the actuation envelope is built. The actuation envelope defines the maximum recoverable stresses and strains that an SMA active element can generate under specific loading conditions. To build the said actuation envelope, a series of experiments are conducted with a dedicated test bench. As shown on Fig. 3, the following heating sequences are applied to the SMA wires starting at point O: the fixed-support stress generation mode (O-C), the stress-free strain

recovery mode (O-G), and a mixed fixed-support / constant-stress mode at different stress levels (O-E₁, O-E₂ and O-E₃). When points C, E₁, E₂, E₃ and G are connected, the resulting curve combined with the O-C and O-G lines delimit the actuation envelope of the active element being tested. All the possible stress-strain trajectories this active element can provide will necessarily be contained within this envelope; the larger the envelope, the greater the overall working generation capacity of the active element.

Note that line GC is extrapolated to intersect the y-axis: point D corresponds to a stress that could be generated if a sufficiently rigid fixture was used. It can be observed that such an envelope could also be drawn using only two testing modes: stress-free (point G) and fixed-support (point C) testing. This strategy has been used to plot the actuation envelope for different maximum actuation temperatures. In Fig. 3, this temperature was set at 150°C .

Fig. 3. Actuation envelope of an individual SMA wire actuator.

1.3 Design diagram

A combination of the host structure stiffness plots (Fig. 2) and the SMA actuation envelopes obtained for several maximum actuation temperatures (Fig. 3) gives the design diagram shown in Fig. 4. Basically, this design diagram indicates at which temperature the actuators must be heated to obtain a desired radius of curvature of the panel. The greater the distance between the actuators, and therefore the smaller their number, the higher the activation temperature required to reach the same radius of curvature.

For example, for a distance between actuators of 20 mm, a radius of curvature of 195 mm will be reached when the actuators are heated to up to 100°C . The same deformed geometry can also be obtained with an inter-actuator distance of 30 mm and wire temperature of 125°C . Therefore, a trade-

off between the actuation temperature (energy needed for activation) and the number of active elements (weight of the panel) can be considered. Note also that the higher the actuation temperature, the shorter the functional fatigue life of the actuators. Note that a 150 mm radius exceeds the capacity of this adaptive panel and cannot be reached under any conditions.

Fig. 4. Preliminary design diagram.

2 Experimental validation

A 425 mm x 425 mm panel is fabricated by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding with four 0.3 mm thick T-300 uniaxial carbon plies oriented at 90° relative to the actuator. The sheaths, which are tubular Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) extrusions, are disposed in a parallel array between the third and the fourth plies of the laminate with a 20 mm distance between them for a total of 19 sheaths. The Araldite 8605 epoxy resin with a high transition temperature is used in the panel.

During the infusion in the direction perpendicular to that of the sheaths to favor uniform flow, the SMA active elements normally inserted into the sheaths are temporarily replaced by stainless steel wires. The reason for this replacement is to avoid any possible alteration of the SMA properties during the cure that follows the infusion. Indeed, after infusion, the panel is cured according to the following sequence: 24 h at room temperature, 2 h at 121°C and 3 h at 177°C. After curing, the stainless steel wires are replaced by the SMA elements that are fixed with screws to two rigid steel members to allow the force transmission between the active and the passive components of the adaptive panel.

Fig. 5 shows one of the extremities of the manufactured panel after the extraction of the steel wires. Two sheaths are clearly visible and it is obvious that 20 mm inter-actuator spacing is

sufficient to preserve the panel's integrity between two successive sheaths. Indeed, in the middle of two successive sheaths, there is no resin-rich layer between the third and fourth plies.

Fig. 5. Extremity of a manufactured panel.

A dedicated test bench, shown in Fig. 6, has been designed to morph the manufactured panels. The SMA wires are heated by Joule effect with an electrical current supplied by a RE30-170 (Matsusada Precision inc.) power source connected to the two rigid members at the panel's extremities. The panel's geometry is monitored by an Aramis (GOM) 3D image correlation measuring system. The temperature of two SMA wires is measured using ten K-type thermocouples uniformly distributed along the wire's axial direction (5 thermocouples par wire). The thermocouples are glued inside ten holes drilled as close as possible to the SMA wires and electrically isolated by a polyurethane coating. Temperature data are collected using a midi Logger GL220 (Graphtec).

Fig. 6. Schematization of the testing bench.

A test is performed with all 19 SMA wires heated simultaneously, which corresponds to an inter-actuator distance of 20 mm. The Aramis 3D image correlation measuring system is configured to take a set of two images (from the left and right cameras) per second. Thus, the entire panel geometry is measured at each second of the heating and cooling phases. Fig. 7 shows the deformed panel.

Fig. 7. Flat panel becoming bended after activation.

The measured perpendicular displacements (in the Z direction) of three cross-sections are given in Fig. 8: section 1 is located in the mid-width of the panel while sections 0 and 2 are located ± 150 mm apart from section 1. All three morphed cross-sections are practically identical, confirming that the panel's properties are uniform and that all the actuators generate similar forces.

Fig. 8. Top: displacements at three specific cross-sections; Bottom: global field of perpendicular displacements.

The Aramis measuring system has the ability to match primitive shapes (circle, plane, cylinder, sphere, etc.) to the measured object. In this case, a cylinder matches almost perfectly the deformed shape of the panel. This last result is important because it validates the preliminary design diagram that has been developed in the first part of the paper. Indeed, since it has been assumed that every part of the panel would deform similarly, then only a small representative part of the panel has been modeled. By measuring a constant radius of curvature over the entire panel, the initial assumption is validated and a single parameter, the radius of curvature, can characterize the deformed shape of the panel. Then, from the measurements, it is possible to plot the panel's radius of curvature as a function of actuators' temperature. In Fig. 9, the black dashed lines correspond to the experimental behaviour, while the solid gray line is the predicted behaviour obtained from the preliminary design diagram.

Fig. 9. Curvature of the panel as a function of actuators' temperature.

A serious concern about the reliable measurement of the wire temperature exists even if all the precautions have been taken during the installation of the thermocouples. In fact, since they are glued into small holes, the thermocouples measure some kind of an average temperature of the SMA wire and surrounding composite laminate. Therefore, it is obvious that the temperature is underestimated. For this reason, the actuators' temperature have been corrected knowing that the panel starts and stops to deform at prescribed temperatures that correspond to the phase transformation temperatures of the SMA wires. These phase transformation temperatures were experimentally characterized for the particular alloy used here. A better measuring technique of the actuators' temperature should be used in the future.

The first observation to be made from Fig. 9 is that the experimental and predicted paths are different, which is mainly caused by the SMAs' hysteretic behavior that hasn't been considered in the preliminary design diagram. The second observation concerns the experimentally measured radii of curvature at the beginning and at the end of one actuation cycle that are not the same (see points A and A' in Fig. 9). Indeed, a residual radius of curvature gradually appears and it increases when the activation cycle is repeated. This is probably due to the local softening of the resin near the heated actuators. The radius of curvature of the experimental panel at the beginning of the test was 335 mm, whereas it was infinitely large (flat panel) for the predicted behaviour. No correction has been used to take into account the resin degradation and resins with better thermal stability should be investigated in the future.

Nevertheless, the PDD was able to predict very accurately the minimal radius of curvature of the panel when the actuators were heated up to their maximal temperature. Indeed, the predicted radius of curvature shows a deviation which is less than a few percent. In short, the displacements are calculated accurately and the PDD can be used to predict the morphed geometry of a panel in which a series of SMA actuators are uniformly distributed.

3 Global finite element model (GFEM)

The preliminary design diagram has basically two main limitations. Firstly, only a panel having a uniform distribution of actuators can be analysed. Indeed, if the actuators are not parallel one to the other or if they are not uniformly distributed, the PDD will then fail to adequately predict the deformed geometry. Secondly, the stacking sequence of the plies must be identical at every point of the panel. It is therefore impossible to study, for example, the effect of stiffening the laminate by adding locally a ply.

In order to predict the effect of any possible arrangement of actuators (number, location within the laminate, orientation, etc.) and composite laminate (number, type and orientation of each ply), the entire panel must then be modeled, not only a small representative section as in the PDD approach. Unfortunately, if the same 3D solid elements used in the PDD approach were employed to model the entire panel, several millions of elements would be needed and the numerical cost would become

impractical. Therefore, in the GFEM, instead of solid elements, link elements are used to represent the SMA active elements, whereas beam and shell elements are selected for the host panel as shown in Fig. 10. Similarly to [18], the beams are added to represent the effect of the laminate thickening near the actuator location. The selection of these finite elements allows the computing time to be minimized.

Fig. 10. General view of the global finite element model.

Note that a more realistic constitutive relation describing the complex nonlinear, temperature dependant and hysteretic behavior of SMAs needs to be considered. In this project, the material law developed by [19] based on the micromechanical formulation of Likhachev has been successfully implemented in ANSYS, but this discussion is beyond of the scope of this paper. Therefore, for sake of simplicity, the SMA behaviour is still simulated according to the same approach as in the PDD, i.e. fixing a negative thermal expansion to the actuators in order to simulate their contraction upon heating. More details are given in [20].

3.1 Presentation of the model

The GFEM combines two-node link, three-node beam and eight-node rectangular shell elements (respectively LINK180, BEAM189 and SHELL281 element types of Ansys). Similarly to the SOLID186 element type used in the PDD, SHELL281 elements can easily represent a laminated structure. This being said, two specific geometrical aspects concerning this model must be addressed, namely i) the actuator position within the host panel and ii) the dimensions and position of the beam elements.

As shown in Fig. 11, the actuator position z_{act} is assumed to be equal to the sum of the thickness of the plies below the actuator (t_{low}), the sheath wall

thickness and the half the diameter of the actuator ($\varnothing_{act}/2$), which gives $z_{act}=1.7$ mm. This value is larger than the total thickness of the laminate ($t_{low} + t_{up} = 1.2$ mm) and that is why the actuator is drawn outside the laminate in Fig. 11. Visual inspections of the manufactured samples (see Fig. 5 for instance) confirm this fact.

Fig. 11. Section view of the global finite element model.

If only shell elements were employed to model the host panel, the local thickening of the structure related to the presence of actuators and sheaths could not be considered. To overcome this issue, beam elements are added to locally increase the panel's inertia. These beam elements are oriented along the actuator length and to minimize the number of parameters to be set, it is assumed that the added beams have a full circular section and that they are positioned tangentially to the upper layer of the host panel. Afterward, an iterative process is engaged to calculate the appropriate beam cross-section diameter (\varnothing_{beam} in Fig. 11) that matches the response given by the finite element model used in the PDD made entirely of solid elements.

Fig. 12 compares the radius of curvature and the maximal deflection as a function of the induced axial strain for three different models: 1) the model made of solid elements used to construct the PDD, 2) the GFEM with beam elements and 3) the GFEM without beam elements.

Fig. 12. Validation of the GFEM.

Deviations larger than 55 % are observed when the beam elements are not included in the GFEM. Based on the good correlation shown in Fig. 12 between the two other models, it is clear that GFEM with beam elements represents a good alternative that produces similar results as the model built with solid elements while using significantly less nodes. For comparison purposes, the model made of solid elements used to build the PDD is composed of more than 300,000 nodes (Fig. 13) compared with the 1,000 nodes required by the GFEM with beam elements (Fig. 14) in order to simulate the same portion of the adaptive panel.

Fig. 13. Finite element mesh made of solid elements with more than 300,000 nodes.

Fig. 14. Finite element mesh made of link, beam and shell elements with approximately 1,000 nodes.

3.2 Case study

The simulation presented in this section is carried out to demonstrate the versatility of the GFEM. By activating 10 of the 19 actuators on only half-width of the panel, warping is induced. The panel is clamped at only one of its four sides. Thereby, the radius of curvature is no longer constant through the panel width. Dimensions of the modeled adaptive panel are chosen according to the manufactured prototype: 425 mm by 425 mm panel with a 20 mm inter-actuator distance. This leads to a model composed of 1,060 LINK180 elements, 1,071 BEAM189 elements and 3,392 SHELL281 elements

for a total of 11,481 nodes (see Fig. 15). Fig. 16 shows the resulting perpendicular displacements when the maximal temperature is reached. It is obvious that these displacements are no longer constant along the y axis. Warping of the panel is then simulated.

Fig. 15. Finite element mesh of the entire panel.

Fig. 16. Overview of the panel warping.

This simulation illustrates a significant benefit of modeling the whole panel brought by the GFEM approach. Indeed, it would not be possible to induce such warping with only a panel section modeled with symmetries. Thus, this introduces a whole range of possible simulations where the actuators could be embedded along multiple directions within the laminate, and this while using a very limited number of nodes. Also, the boundary conditions can easily be modified and initially curved panel can be studied.

Conclusions

The objective of this paper was to present two complementary approaches for designing adaptive laminated composite panels with embedded SMA actuators. An experimental validation of both models has been successfully performed using an especially manufactured 425 mm x 425 mm adaptive panel containing 19 parallel SMA actuators. It has been shown that a significant reduction of the number of nodes, and thus of the computation time, is possible when solid elements are replaced by link, beam and shell elements.

Even if difficulties have been encountered with the experimental measurements of the temperature of the SMA actuator embedded in the panel, the deformed shape of the adaptive panel is properly predicted. Finally, the model versatility has also been demonstrated by simulating the panel's warping when only one half of the panel is activated.

Altogether, it can be asserted that a global finite element model using shell, beam and link element can be employed as a design tool to simulate, with a minimal computation cost, numerous configurations of the panel that involve different number and orientation of the composite plies and different number, position and orientation of SMA wire actuators.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the National Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC) for their financial support through the Discovery grant of Professor Terriault and École de technologie supérieure (ETS) for the postgraduate scholarships of S. Lacasse and C. Simoneau.

References

- [1] G. Lesueur, T. Merlet, M. Queguiner, P. Granger, F. Renault, H. Gilles and S. Girard "Management of deformable active antenna". *Proceedings of the Radar 2009 conference - Surveillance for a Safer World*, pp 1-5, 2009.
- [2] I. Kanno, T. Kunisawa, T. Suzuki and H. Kotera "Development of deformable mirror composed of piezoelectric thin films for adaptive optics". *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics*, Vol. 13, No. 2, pp 155-161, 2007.
- [3] G. Rodrigues, R. Bastais and A. Preumont "Morphing of segmented bimorph mirrors". *International Journal of Optomechatronics*, Vol. 4, No. 3, pp 217-236, 2010.
- [4] N. Bioria and V. Sumini "Performative Building Skin Systems: A Morphogenomic Approach Towards Developing Real-Time Adaptive Building Skin Systems". *International Journal of Architectural Computing*, Vol. 7, No. 4, pp 643-676, 2009.

- [5] D. Coutu, V. Brailovski and P. Terriault "Optimized design of an active extrados structure for an experimental morphing laminar wing". *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 14, No. 7, pp 451-458, 2010.
- [6] L.D. Peel, J. Mejia, B. Narvaez, K. Thompson and M. Lingala "Development of a simple morphing wing using elastomeric composites as skins and actuators". *Journal of Mechanical Design*, Transactions of the ASME, Vol. 131, No. 9, 0910031-0910038, 2009.
- [7] A.Y.N. Sofla, S.A. Meguid, K.T. Tan and W.K. Yeo "Shape morphing of aircraft wing: Status and challenges". *Materials and Design*, Vol. 31, No. 3, pp 1284-1292, 2010.
- [8] C. Thill, J.A. Etches, I.P. Bond, K.D. Potter and P.M. Weaver "Composite corrugated structures for morphing wing skin applications". *Smart Materials and Structures*, Vol. 19, No. 12, 124009 (10 pp.), 2010.
- [9] Y.L. Young, J.W. Baker and M.R. Motley "Reliability-based design and optimization of adaptive marine structures". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 92, No. 2, pp 244-253, 2010.
- [10] S. Barbarino, F. Gandhi and S.D. Webster "Design of extendable chord sections for morphing helicopter rotor blades". *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, Vol. 22, No. 9, pp 891-905, 2011.
- [11] N.A. Koratkar and C. Inderjit "Wind tunnel testing of a Mach-scaled rotor model with trailing-edge flaps". *Smart Materials and Structures*, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp 1-14, 2001.
- [12] S. Daynes and P.M. Weaver "A morphing trailing edge device for a wind turbine". *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, Vol. 23, No. 6, pp 691-701, 2012.
- [13] A. Baz, T. Chen and J. Ro "Shape control of NITINOL-reinforced composite beams". *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 31, no 8, p. 631-642, 2000.
- [14] C. M. Wayman and K. Otsuka, "*Shape memory materials*". 1st edition, Cambridge University Press, 1999.
- [15] G. Zhou and P. Lloyd "Design, manufacture and evaluation of bending behaviour of composite beams embedded with SMA wires". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 69, No. 13, pp 2034-2041, 2009.
- [16] T.L. Turner and H.D. Patel "Analysis of SMA hybrid composite structures in MSC.Nastran and ABAQUS". *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, Vol. 18, No. 5, pp 435-447, 2007.
- [17] S. Lacasse, "Design, fabrication and characterization of adaptive composite panels actuated by shape memory alloy wires " (in French), *Master thesis*, École de technologie supérieure, Montreal, Canada, 2013.
- [18] S.P. Thompson and J. Loughlan "The control of the post-buckling response in thin composite plates using smart technology". *Thin-Walled Structures*, Vol. 36, No. 4, pp 231-263, 2000.
- [19] P. Terriault and V. Brailovski "Modeling of shape memory alloy actuators using Likhachev's formulation". *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, Vol. 22, pp. 353-368, 2011.
- [20] C. Simoneau, "Modeling of adaptive composite panels actuated by shape memory alloy wires" (in French), *Master thesis*, École de technologie supérieure, Montreal, Canada, 2013.